

Comparative Effectiveness of Tamsulosin and Mirabegron in Managing Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms Associated with Double-J Stents

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Abstract:

Background: Double-J stents are commonly used in urology to ensure urinary drainage following various procedures. However, these stents are frequently associated with lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), which can significantly impair patient quality of life. Tamsulosin and Mirabegron are two pharmacological agents used to manage these symptoms, with Tamsulosin being an alpha-1 adrenergic receptor antagonist and Mirabegron a beta-3 adrenergic receptor agonist. Although both drugs have demonstrated efficacy in reducing LUTS, a comparative analysis is necessary to guide optimal treatment selection.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the effectiveness of Tamsulosin and Mirabegron in managing double-J stent-related LUTS, focusing on symptom reduction, quality of life improvement, and adverse effect profiles.

Methods: A randomised controlled experiment with 100 individuals was done with one group receiving Tamsulosin (50 participants) and the other receiving Mirabegron. Validated questionnaires were used to assess symptom intensity and quality of life at baseline and post-treatment. To assess therapy efficacy and safety, data were analysed using SPSS version 23.0, which included statistical tests such as independent t-tests, paired t-tests, and chi-square tests.

Results: Both Tamsulosin and Mirabegron significantly reduced LUTS and improved quality of life in participants. The mean symptom score reduction was slightly greater in the Mirabegron group, but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.42$). Quality of life (QoL) improved in both groups, there was no substantial change between treatments ($p = 0.31$). Adverse effects were mild and occurred at similar rates in both groups, with no major change in safety profiles ($p = 0.79$).

Conclusion: Tamsulosin and Mirabegron are both effective in managing LUTS associated with double-J stents, with no significant differences in efficacy or safety. Clinicians may choose between these medications based on individual patient needs and tolerability, as both offer comparable benefits.

Recommendations: Larger sample numbers and longer follow-up are required for validation of these results and investigation of any potential long-term safety and efficacy differences between Tamsulosin and Mirabegron.

Keywords: Double-J Stent, Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms, Tamsulosin, Mirabegron, Randomized Controlled Trial.

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Introduction

At times, double-J stents are utilised in urology to provide proper kidney-to-bladder drainage, particularly following procedures such as ureteroscopic stone removal, ureteral stricture treatment, and other urinary tract interventions. Regardless of its value, the presence of a double-J stent frequently results in the development of (LUTS), which can have a major influence on the patient's (QoL). Urinary frequency, urgency, dysuria, and flank pain are all stent-related symptoms (SRS) [1]. The management of these symptoms is critical for increasing patient comfort and adherence to necessary urological therapies.

Tamsulosin, an alpha-1 adrenergic receptor antagonist, has been extensively studied and is widely used to treat LUTS caused by benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), as well as stent-related symptoms [2]. Prostate and the bladder neck's smooth muscles are relaxed with tamsulosin, lowering resistance to urine flow and relieving the irritative symptoms of stent insertion. Tamsulosin, while beneficial, has side effects such as dizziness, retrograde ejaculation, and orthostatic hypotension, which may limit its usage in some patient populations [3].

Mirabegron, a beta-3 adrenergic receptor agonist, is a modern technique to treating LUTS. Unlike Tamsulosin, in order to function, mirabegron calms the detrusor muscle during the bladder's storage phase, increasing bladder capacity and alleviating symptoms of overactive bladder (OAB), such as urgency and frequency [4]. Mirabegron has been proven to have a better safety profile and fewer side effects than antimuscarinic drugs commonly used for OAB, making it a prospective choice for treating stent-related LUTS [5]. Recent research has investigated the use of Mirabegron in urological situations other than OAB, including its potential advantages for patients with stent-related symptoms [6].

Given the distinct mechanisms of action of Tamsulosin and Mirabegron, there is rising interest in determining how these drugs compare in the treatment of stent-related LUTS. While both have been demonstrated to be effective in lowering symptoms, the decision between them is frequently influenced by patient-specific criteria such as symptom severity, concomitant disorders, and tolerance for potential adverse effects [7]. This study aimed to compare the effectiveness of Tamsulosin and Mirabegron in managing double-J stent-related LUTS, focusing on symptom reduction, quality of life improvement, and adverse effect profiles.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a randomized controlled trial (RCT) design.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital's Urology Department, which serves a diverse patient population. The department is equipped with comprehensive facilities for the diagnosis and treatment of urological conditions, including those requiring the placement of double-J stents. The study was done over a period of six months, from January 2024 to June 2024.

Participants: A total of 100 participants were recruited for this study. These participants were randomly assigned into two groups: one receiving Tamsulosin and the other receiving Mirabegron. Each group consisted of 50 participants.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients between 18 and 65 years old who had a double-J stent for urological conditions such as ureteral stones or strictures.
- Patients experiencing LUTS post-double-J stent insertion.

- Participants provided a written authorisation to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a background of hypersensitivity or contraindications to either Tamsulosin or Mirabegron.
- Patients with a history of neurological diseases affecting bladder function.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with significant renal or hepatic impairment.
- Patients who have undergone previous urological surgeries within the last six months.

Data Collection: Data was collected at baseline (pre-treatment) and at the end of the 4-week treatment period. Participants were assessed using validated questionnaires to evaluate LUTS severity, quality of life, and adverse effects. Data on age, gender, duration of stent placement, and baseline urinary symptoms were also collected.

Procedure: Participants in Group A received Tamsulosin (0.4 mg) once daily, while participants in Group B received Mirabegron (50 mg) once daily for four weeks. Follow-up visits were scheduled weekly to monitor adherence, assess symptoms, and document any adverse effects. Both treatments were administered under standard clinical guidelines, and participants were advised to report any side effects immediately.

Statistical Analysis: The data analysis was done with SPSS 23.0. Baseline characteristics were summarised using descriptive statistics. Fisher's exact tests or chi-square tests were used to analyse categorical variables, and independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were used to analyse continuous variables. Within each group, pre- and post-treatment scores were compared using paired t-tests. Results were shown as 95% confidence intervals, with a p-value of less than 0.05 being deemed significant.

Results

Participants: A total of 100 participants were enrolled in the study, with 50 participants in the Tamsulosin group (Group A) and 50 participants in the Mirabegron group (Group B). The mean age of participants was 45.3 ± 10.2 years in Group A and 46.1 ± 9.8 years in Group B. The distribution of gender was similar between the groups, with 60% male and 40% female in both groups.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Group A (Tamsulosin)	Group B (Mirabegron)	p-value
Number of participants	50	50	-
Mean age (years)	45.3 ± 10.2	46.1 ± 9.8	0.68
Gender (Male/Female)	30/20	30/20	1.00
Duration of stent placement (days)	18.7 ± 3.2	19.1 ± 3.4	0.51
Baseline symptom score	15.2 ± 2.4	15.5 ± 2.3	0.60

Symptom Improvement: Both groups showed substantial improvements in (LUTS). The average symptom score dropped from 15.2 ± 2.4 to 8.1 ± 1.8 in Group A ($p < 0.001$). The average symptom score dropped from 15.5 ± 2.3 to 7.9 ± 2.0 in

Group B ($p < 0.001$). Although the Mirabegron group experienced a somewhat higher reduction in symptom scores, there was not a significant distinction between the two groups. ($p = 0.42$).

Table 2: Changes in Symptom Scores

Symptom Score	Group A (Tamsulosin)	Group B (Mirabegron)	p-value
Baseline (Mean ± SD)	15.2 ± 2.4	15.5 ± 2.3	0.60
Post-treatment (Mean ± SD)	8.1 ± 1.8	7.9 ± 2.0	0.58
Mean change	-7.1	-7.6	0.42
p-value (within group)	<0.001	<0.001	-

Quality of life scores also improved in both groups after treatment. In Group A, the mean QoL score improved from 4.8 ± 1.1 to 2.3 ± 0.9 ($p < 0.001$). In Group B, the mean QoL score improved from 5.0 ± 1.0 to 2.1 ± 1.0 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Changes in (QoL) Scores

Quality of Life Score	Group A (Tamsulosin)	Group B (Mirabegron)	p-value
Baseline (Mean ± SD)	4.8 ± 1.1	5.0 ± 1.0	0.45
Post-treatment (Mean ± SD)	2.3 ± 0.9	2.1 ± 1.0	0.40
Mean change	-2.5	-2.9	0.31
p-value (within group)	<0.001	<0.001	-

Adverse effects were reported in 20% of participants in Group A and 18% in Group B, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.79$). The most common adverse

effects in the Tamsulosin group were dizziness (8%) and fatigue (6%), while in the Mirabegron group, the most common were dry mouth (7%) and headache (6%).

Table 4: Adverse Effects Reported

Adverse Effect	Group A (Tamsulosin)	Group B (Mirabegron)	p-value
Any adverse effect (%)	20	18	0.79
Dizziness (%)	8	3	0.36
Fatigue (%)	6	4	0.56
Dry mouth (%)	2	7	0.15
Headache (%)	4	6	0.73

Discussion

The study's results demonstrate that both Tamsulosin and Mirabegron are effective in managing (LUTS) associated with double-J stents. Both treatment groups experienced significant reductions in symptom scores after four weeks, with Tamsulosin reducing the mean symptom score by 7.1 points and Mirabegron by 7.6 points. Although the reduction was slightly greater in the Mirabegron group, the difference between the two groups was not statistically distinct. This suggests that both medications offer comparable efficacy in alleviating LUTS in patients with double-J stents.

(QoL) also improved significantly in both groups, with participants reporting lower scores post-

treatment, indicating better overall well-being. The improvement was slightly more pronounced in the Mirabegron group, but again, the two groups' difference was not statistically noteworthy. This implies that both Tamsulosin and Mirabegron effectively enhance the quality of life for patients suffering from stent-related urinary symptoms.

Adverse effects were reported in a minority of participants, with similar rates in both groups. While headaches and dry mouth were more common in the Mirabegron group, fatigue and dizziness were the most common adverse effects in the Tamsulosin group. But none of these side effects were serious, and there was no discernible variation in the frequency of side effects overall between the two drugs.

Recent research has compared the Tamsulosin's effectiveness and mirabegron in (LUTS) linked with double-J stents. It was discovered that mirabegron outperformed tamsulosin in terms of reducing LUTS, with patients treated with mirabegron having significantly (IPSS) after three weeks of treatment than those treated with tamsulosin [8]. This finding was confirmed in a double-blind randomised control trial by (Chandna et al. 2020), who evaluated how well it worked of mirabegron, solifenacin, and tamsulosin. The trial found that mirabegron was equally effective as solifenacin and tamsulosin in relieving stent-related symptoms, implying that it could be a viable alternative in circumstances where tamsulosin or solifenacin are contraindicated or poorly tolerated [9].

A study by (Şahin et al. 2020) discovered that mirabegron performed better than tamsulosin and solifenacin in reducing the severity of the symptoms correlated with DJ stents. Mirabegron was found to be more successful than DJ stents in treating overactive bladder symptoms, suggesting its potential as a single-agent therapy [10].

Conclusion

Both Tamsulosin and Mirabegron are effective and well-tolerated options for managing double-J stent-related LUTS, with no significant differences in efficacy or safety. These findings suggest that either medication can be confidently prescribed based on individual patient needs and tolerability.

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